

EXPRESSION OF ANIMISTIC AND TOTEMISTIC VIEWS IN MAGIC TALES

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Abstract. This article analyzes the animistic and totemistic views in the magic tales of the Uzbek people.

Key words. Fairy tales, magical tales, animistic visions, totemistic visions, primitive visions.

Fairy tales reflect the flight of the people's intelligence, the thousand-year wisdom of the people's dreams, their desire to know the problems of eternal life based on metaphorical symbols of their experience.

In some magical tales we see the expression of ancient animistic concepts. This situation can sometimes be seen in fairy tales when the soul of a giant or fairies is located in another place. For example, "Qiron Botir"¹. In the fairy tale, it is described that the souls of fairies are in pigeons. Such views are also related to the imagination of primitive people.

Among Uzbek folk tales, magical tales occupy a special place. They are very diverse and colorful in terms of artistic plot. In this sense, we would like to mention that their scientific study and evaluation based on new scientific concepts

¹Хоразм эртақлари. Ўзадабийнашр. – Т.: 1961. 77-бет.

is not satisfactory. Russian scientists V.Y. Propp in his “Historical Roots of Magical Tales”² in his work, V.M. Zhirmunsky “Epic of Turkish heroism”³, V.P. Anikin “Tales of the Russian people”⁴. In his scientific works, some comments were made about the reflection of animism and totemism in magical tales. However, the animistic and totemistic views of Uzbek folk tales have not been fully expressed in the scientific works mentioned above.

In magical fairy tales, it is noticeable that everything surrounding the hero moves and comes to life. For example, the life of fairies in the country where the hero goes is similar to people, or the characters turn into animals or other things, and other moments can be seen, all of which are manifestations of animism in different forms. In the same place, you can also remember Semurgh, who talks like a man and eats in his own way.

In Central Asian herding peoples, they do not step on the bones of cattle, they treat animals that have a sign different from other animals in a special way, they consider that animal to bring happiness, they do not kill owls, red jays, blue crows, at the same time they look at white snakes, owl with faith. There are also legends that the person who sees the feet of the king will be the happiest person.

The totemistic views of ancient people are also reflected in magical tales. For example, the king's daughter gave birth to Arpapolvon⁵, the snake groom who married the king's youngest daughter⁶, tales of the poor old woman's wonderful frog daughter⁷ we can see. Especially, the image of the stork, which brings happiness, depicted in fairy tales, attracts one's attention. He also makes the poor

²Пропп В. Я. Сехрли эртақларнинг тарихий илдижи. – Л., 1946.

³Жирмунский В. М. Тюркиский героический эпос. – Л., 1974.

⁴Аникин В.П. Русская народная сказка. – М., 1959.

⁵Гулпар. 38-48-бетлар.

⁶Гулпар. 43-45-бетлар.

⁷Гулпар. 192-194-бетлар.

farmer rich and brings him happiness. In fairy tales, the stork is always a positive image, and in magical tales, it is depicted as magical.

In magical fairy tales, we meet the image of various animals that help the hero of the work and help him to achieve his goal. The horse is one of the first helpers of the hero. Horses depicted in magical tales appear as fighters, speakers, foreseeing everything and saving their owner (positive hero) from danger and death. So, the horse is the hero's most reliable, loyal friend. In these tales, the horse is depicted in the same way as in epics.

Although the horses described in magical tales are not as detailed as Girkok and Boychibor in the epics, they play a decisive role in the hero's movement towards the goal. In Abulqasim's fairy tale, white, yellow and black vulture horses help the brothers to fulfill the conditions of the princesses and marry them. This, of course, is related to the fact that the horse plays an important role in people's lives, especially in the lives of cattle farmers. A wolf, a fairy, a snake, an eagle, a sable as a hero's helper in magical tales, stork and similar images can be seen.

In magical tales, animals always return kindness with kindness. For example, one can remember the images of dog, cat and snake in the fairy tale “Mehrigiyo”, which is very common among the Uzbek people⁸.

In general, the animistic and totemistic views of our ancient ancestors were expressed in most of the Uzbek folk magic tales. The important thing is that this situation in magical fairy tales not only makes the plot interesting, but also has a great educational value.

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⁸Gulpari. Pages 31-38.

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